

SOCIO-SEMANTIC STUDY OF IZERE PERSONAL NAME PRACTICES OF PLATEAU STATE BETWEEN
the 1990s-2000s

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Abstract

This study is a fusion of two different linguistic fields of studies joint to become one. These two fields are sociolinguistics and semantics. The sociolinguistic aspect deals with the aspect of naming a newborn in a society i.e. how names are given and derived while the semantic aspect deals with the meaning and origin of the names i.e using two eras 1960s-1990s and the early 1990s-2000s in which names and naming system have been affected, how a name is used in the Izere language and how names have changed over a period using three factors which are the social, historical and religious factors. The Afizere are a group of people who are mainly found in Plateau State, North Central Nigeria and speakers of the Izere language. They are also popularly known as the "Jarawa" by the Hausa and other non-speakers. The research was able to identify and analyse male and female names in the Izere language. The researchers adopted the Sapir-Whorf hypothesis and the Descriptivist theory of names as the theoretical framework. The first claims the relationship between language and culture which determines how the speaker of a language views the world (Sapir 200) while the latter claims that the meaning of the name is identical to the descriptions associated with it by speakers, while the referent is determined to be the object that satisfies the description. Data were collected via interviews with native speakers of Izere language and questionnaire, presented in the table and analysed via prose description. At the end of this research, the researchers were able to discover the reasons why names and naming systems have changed over a period, which was what prompted the study, and the importance of preserving the Izere language in written forms to prevent it from going extinct. The study is significant as it recommends the importance of encouraging speakers of the Izere language to use their indigenous native names for easy identification and also all names in different periods should be appreciated and used freely without discrimination.

Keywords: Socio-Semantic, Study, Izere, Personal, Practices and Plateau, State.

I. Introduction

Naming is a very interesting aspect thus, naming, we can say, originated way back in the time of Adam and Eve in the creation of the earth; where God instructed Adam to name all the animals, plants and even his companion, Eve in the Garden of Eden. Names are related to ethics and culture in every region, as well as the history of families and social groups. This means that a name is a clue to an identity of an entity. Hence, every culture has its naming pattern and meanings based on their personal view of the world using their spoken language. This is to say that people are inspired to name a child by natural conditions, circumstances, virtues, future expectations, animals, days of the week, events, festivals and seasons. Naming is however very important and vital process especially in the life of a newborn. This is because the name gives the newborn baby a means of identity that sets him/her apart from anyone. Hence, the meanings behind a name of a child should reflect something of greatness and purpose which prepares a child for the future unknown (Lupenga 2006).

The study decided to separate these names into two eras i.e. names commonly used in

the 1960-1990 and names commonly used in the 2000s about three factors which are social, historical and religious. How these factors have affected names and naming systems in the Izere language thereby striking a balance as to why some names changed over time in these eras and how relevant these names are in the present century formed the worry of the study.

The Izere People and Language

The Afizere are a group of people who are mainly found in Plateau State, North Central Nigeria and speakers of the Izere language. They are also popularly known as the "Jarawa" by the Hausa and other non-speakers. They are found mainly in Jos East, Jos North Local Government and others in the parts of Miango (Irigwe) in Bassa Local Government of Plateau state. In other states you can also find the Afizeres are in Bauchi and Kaduna states. In Bauchi State, they are found in Toro, Tafawa Balewa and Dass Local Government areas respectively because of the shared boundary they have with Plateau State and in Kaduna state, they are found in the parts of Kagoro and Chawai according to Musa (1988). The Afizere people are popularly known with other names such as the Afizere, Afizilek, Jarawa, Bajari and Afusare (afizereworld.org).

According to Roger and Kaze (2006), the Afizere people are speakers of the Izere language. There are five dialects spoken by the Afizere people which are; the Ibor dialect largely spoken in the Fobur, Isum, spoken in Fursum; Afuganang, in Shere; Afudelek in Federe and Akyo in Maigemu respectively. These districts share the same cultural values with a slight difference in the dialects spoken. However, the Izere language is also known for other alternative names such as the Izilek, Fusare and Fizere and these names are based on dialectal variation in these districts.

According to David (1998), there are five (5) main districts and they are headed by a single ruler known as the Ada Agwom, meaning king/ruler. He is seen and regarded as the supreme head who oversees all aspects of affairs that concern the Afizere people. These five districts are the Fobur, Fursum, Federe, Maigem and the Shere which in turn have other minor villages/clans with each speaking different dialects or near similar dialects of the Izere language. In Fobur district, they speak the Ibor dialect and they are called the Afuborah consisting of other minor villages/ clans such as Fobur Pada, Fobur Kasa, Fusa, Gwafan, Fudawa, Zarazon and Laminga. In Fursum district, they speak the Isum dialect which is closely related to the dialect spoken in the Federe district that is the Afudelek. Again, we have the Maigemu district, they are called Isum/Fisum and they consist of clans/villages like; Tere, Birtu, Foron, Juwa Angwa, Gwaji and Kerang.

In recent times, with the advent of religion and the computer age generation, the Izere language is seen to be greatly endangered and maybe gradually going extinct. Language endangerment has been a basic concern for several decades for many reasons where smaller languages are dominated by other languages known to be the standard language. For instance, where a speaker of the Izere language stops using his/her indigenous language and drops its cultural values and completely adopts the culture and language of other people e.g. English language and Hausa which are frequently used languages in most homes of Izere speakers.

The Concept of Name

Names, as words by which reality is known and spoken of, are the most meaningful lexicon in the vocabulary of any language, and they are an important part of the language inventory as they not only name the environment but also store all the distinctions about the fauna and flora (Lupenga 2006). He shades more light by viewing the movement of slaves from Africa to New World thus: 'When slaves were captured know the African continent and brought

to the New World, they brought with them names as the means to identify their environment and themselves (2006). To Ullmann (1962), names play such an important role in human relations that they are often endowed with magic potency and surrounded by elaborate superstitions and taboos. In the words of John, a name is more than a label or a mere arrangement of sounds and letters. Bound up with names, there is history, legend, and fact (1977). Hence, we may say that a name is a word by which something or someone is known.

Moyo, viewing Suzma's assertion, observes that yes, there is also an indication that community members act as original givers of names, but yet, names vary and are extensive, and they point to historical events and social circumstances within the larger family units (2002). He further opines that the act of naming oneself, therefore, shows that names serve as indicators of broader social change and names are a device that explains and classifies patterns of domination and submission (2002).

According to Nuessel (1992), for most, choosing a name for a newborn is an activity of utmost significance. The act of naming a newborn is an important rite of passage in society or any given culture. Making a name announcement to family members, filling the birth certificate, holding a formal religious or cultural naming ceremony all represent a process of individuation in which a newborn becomes a separate entity that will ultimately develop a unique personality. Nuessel (1992) also attests that most people recognize that giving a name to a newborn is a significant social function with profound and lifelong consequences.

Putting into cognizance the postulations above, it can be said that cultural background, attitudes, beliefs and physical environment are non-linguistic factors of naming such that every society and ethnic group has its own tradition when it comes to naming their newborn. Parents tend to give names to their children that will not violate their social norms and customs such that certain names are passed on within the same family to prevent the name from dying. This serves as a reminder of the real origin of the names as signs of continuity and remembrance which is why children are named after their grandparents, great grandparents, uncles, aunts or even distant relatives which is a common factor in the Izere culture.

The Concept of Semantics

Semantics is said to be an ancient Greek word that means significance. It is the linguistic and philosophical study that deals with meaning in language, programming languages, formal logic and semiotics. It is concerned with the relationship between signifiers like words, phrases, signs and symbols and what they stand for.

Since we know that language is used to express meaning which can be understood by others, meaning we can say exists only in our minds through logical thoughts and speaker's view of the world using language hence; we express it through spoken or written forms, gestures and actions.

To Lyons (1977), semantics is the study of meaning systematically encoded in the vocabulary/ grammar of the natural language. This definition claims that meaning is reflected in any language hence for every word or name that exists, there is a meaning behind its existence. This makes it unique in the language. Benjamin Lee Whorf in his study stresses the intimate relationship between the internal structure of a given language and how a speaker classifies words around him using the physical environment around which in turn affects a speaker's view and perception.

According to Lobner (2002), semantics can be defined as the part of linguistics that studies the meanings of linguistic expressions, either simple or complex, taken in isolation. This

definition further accounts for utterance meaning i.e. the meaning of an expression used in a concrete context of utterance about the expressed meaning (2002). This goes to say that, for every utterance in a conversation, meaning is a key factor to understanding one another.

Saeed (2009) defines semantics as the scientific study of the meaning of words and meanings of a language. Therefore, meaning and communication have a strong connection where communication is used to exchange or relay information, attitudes, feelings and values from one person to another which is done mainly through the use of language. According to the definition, this is to say that, a meaningful conversation is spoken through the channel called language and the expressive meaning must be properly portrayed to the listener for effective understanding.

II. Theoretical Framework

The researchers adopted the Sapir-Whorf hypothesis and the Descriptivist theory of names as the theoretical framework. The Sapir- Whorf hypothesis claims the relationship between language and culture which determines how the speaker of a language views the world. Sapir acknowledges the relationship between language, culture and the world. He maintains that they are inextricably related hence one cannot understand or appreciate one without the other. The idea in this hypothesis is that every human being views the world in his native language (Sapir 2017).

In Whorfs' view, the relationship between language and culture is a deterministic one; that social category we create and how we perceive events and actions are constrained by the language we speak. Different speakers will therefore experience the world differently so far as the languages they speak differ structurally. One claim is that if speakers of one language have certain words to describe things and speakers of another language lack similar words, and then speakers of the first language will find it easier to talk about those things. Another claim is that if one language makes distinctions that another does not make, and then those who use the language will more readily perceive the relevant differences in their environment. Hence, a speaker's world view is solely dependent on how he/she views the world through its language but also at the same time limits such perception. Speakers of different languages, therefore, have different worldviews.

To them, one cannot appreciate one without the knowledge of the other. Wardhaugh, in one of his claims on the shared relationship between language and culture, asserts thus:

The structure of a language determines how a speaker of that language views the world or; as a weaker view, the structure does not determine the world-view but is still extremely influential in predisposing speakers of a language towards adopting their world-view (2011).

Similarly, the belief that the world view of a speaker is shaped by the language spoken and that the nature of language and how the world is viewed by its speakers are significantly connected. It, therefore, means that the background linguistic system of each language is not merely a reproducing instrument for voicing ideas but rather the shaper of ideas and perception.

The descriptivist theory of names, sometimes called Frege- Russell theory, claims that the meaning or semantic content of a name is identical to the descriptions associated with it by speakers, while the referent is determined to be the object that satisfies the description. In this sense, this theory seeks to say that for every name to come to existence, there is some collection of descriptions associated with that constitute of the name in the first place. This is to say that the referent name is what satisfies all or most of the description.

Although, the researchers are of the view that not all names have a physical referent object to which they refer to in the Izere language according to the descriptivist theory and this is because some names come into existence as a result of family history, birth circumstances, social effect or religious effect and until these stories are told meanings cannot be drawn out directly; examples of such are: Ishun (M), Ina (M), Abbi/Abi (F) etc which account for the use of the context of their usage.

Nonetheless, according to Kripke (1980), the name refers to an object by causal connection with the object as mediated through communications of speakers. He points out that proper names, in contrast to most descriptions are rigid designators; hence, a proper name refers to the named objects in every possible world in which the object or person exists. For instance, the name Agwom refers to a name of a person existing in a particular society belonging to the Afizere culture and the meaning of the name is possibly associated with a crown which means that the name is attached to royalty, therefore, signifying a king. Even though it is given to a child, it does not necessarily mean he is a king but was born during the coronation festival of a king.

In a nutshell, the researchers chose these two theories because they believe that names and naming in any society reflect the world view of the culture of that society. This is because there is a relationship between language and culture hence names and naming subsume the socio-cultural values of every society.

III. Research Methodology

In this study, the method of data collection was primary and secondary sources. An oral interview with the native speakers of the Izere language was conducted to help in the collection and gathering of data. The researchers randomly selected ten (10) elderly Izere speakers ranging from the ages of 55-90 years of age consisting of five (5) males and five (5) females. However, all interviewed persons were chosen based on their knowledge of the language and culture.

The researchers also used a questionnaire, which consisted of series of questions that served as a guideline to help in the development of the work, especially on the names and naming system, birth, how names are derived in the Izere language and so on. Other sources of data collection were the secondary sources through the use of books, encyclopedias and internet research. Data were presented in the table and analysed via prose description respectively.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Choice of Male and Female Names and Meanings commonly in the 1960^s-1990^s

Table 1: Masculine names

NO	NAME	MEANING	ANALYSIS	STRUCTURE
1	Azi	He shall multiply	This name is given to a male child whose parents have undergone series of miscarriages before his arrival as the only surviving child. The survival of the child is likened to that of the termite. He is then professed to	Sentence

			multiply like the termites 'Izih'.	
2	Abok	Chief Priest/ A Physician	This is given to a child whose parents see him become a potential physician, healer or chief priest. The child is seen to become a great helper to people with health challenges in the future.	Phrasal
3	Agwom	King/ Ruler	This is given to a male child born either from a royal family, born on the day a new king was crowned or the parent's future expectation for the child.	Lexical
4	Atu	Blacksmith	This name is given to a child born in a family who are into the profession of a blacksmith. This is called 'Guza' which is a common profession by most Izere speakers.	Lexical
5	Adang	My patience shall prevail	This is a name given to a male child whose parents have long awaited the blessing of a child after several years of childlessness	Sentence

Table 2: Feminine names

NO	NAME	MEANING	ANALYSIS	STRUCTURE
1	Amazi	You shall multiply	This is the female version of the name Azi / Azih. This is when she is also the only surviving child of her parents after	Sentence

			several miscarriages.	
2	Adua	To worship	This is given to a female child regarded as God-sent into a family.	Phrasal
3	Akusang	I shall search no more	This name is given to a female child whose parents have been childless for many years after marriage. Hence, the birth of this child is a sign of contentment and relief.	Sentence
4	Ayong	Sorrow has ended	This is given to a female child born during a mourning period. It could mean the death of a close family relative or someone in the community.	Sentence
5	Adija/Adizha	Be productive always	This is given to a female child born also during 'Ijak' festival.	Sentence

Choice of Male and Female names and meaning commonly in the 2000^s

Table 3: Modern masculine names

NO	NAME	MEANING	ANALYSIS	STRUCTURE
1	Igyem	Brightness	This name is given to a child who is seen to become a star among his peers; that is a child with a great and bright future.	Lexical
2	Anang	Lord has given me	This is given to a male child whose parents believe that it is only God that gives the blessing of children and they	Sentence

			are privileged to have received his blessing.	
3	Ina	It is settled	This is given to a male child whose parents see him as a symbol of peace especially when the child was born during crises or difficulty in the family and his birth settled all the scores.	Sentence
4	Aweng	Good luck	This name is given to a male child who is seen to be a source of good fortune and hence, he would become a success when he grows.	Phrasal
5	Nyam	Good fortune	This is given to a male child whose parents see his birth to be a symbol of good fortune.	Phrasal

Table 4: Modern feminine names

NO	NAME	MEANING	ANALYSIS	STRUCTURE
1	Kushim	Love	This name is given to a female child whose parents regard her as a symbol of love and affection to them and to everyone who comes across the child.	lexical
2	Kusas	Beautiful	This is given to a female child who is regarded as a symbol of beauty to her family by her parents.	Lexical
3	Adar	Star	This is given to a female child who is seen by her parents	Lexical

			to become a shining star among her peers which is a future expectation of every parent.	
4	Mise / Minse	I found my blessing	This is given to a child whose parents see children as a blessing and gift from God.	Sentence
5	Anyazung	Shy lady	This is given to a female child who refused to open her eyes when she was born especially when people came around to visit her. The child is assumed to be a shy person when she grows.	Phrasal

IV. Findings and Conclusion

In the course of this research, the researchers were able to discover how names and naming systems have changed over some time in the Izere language using three basic factors i.e. social, historical and religious factors and that the names can be categorized into structures such as lexical, phrasal and sentence among others.

Another discovery was that some names in the Izere language have the same original, usage and meaning but are spelt differently in names likes Abbi/Abi, Adija/Adizha, Maji/Maje, Mise/Minse, Ajyi/Ijyi. In some cases, they are pronounced differently and this is due to the dialectal variation of the Izere language.

Because names are passed from one generation to the other, the pattern of naming a newborn is thereby affected in the Izere language. For instance, the name Abbi/Abi is given to the only female child born among several boys or the first female child of a family but in most cases is seen given to a second, third, fourth female child born amidst several other female children. This has however distorted the original meaning and usage of the name.

It was also discovered that naming practices in the 1960-1990s which are said to have no prominent meaning because of their sad notes, definitely imply a lot of meaning which can be found in the origin/ historical background of the name bearer. As such, the bad stories behind the given names do not necessarily mean that the bearers of such names will experience an unfortunate event in life but as a reminder of how the name came about.

As the research progressed, it also discovered that the creation of new names in the Izere language over some time has encouraged the use of Izere names by speakers of the Izere language, especially in the contemporary time.

In conclusion, the researchers hope that with this research on the names and naming system, the Izere speakers will have a different perspective to the Izere names and naming

system used in the 1960^s-1990^s and also come to accept and appreciate their names without finding any faults. The researchers also recommend that parents should do proper research on the early names used in the 1960^s-1990^s before assuming that the names used earlier have no meaning. This is why the passing of names through generation is regarded as an important aspect of naming to date.

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